

Customization of UWB Indoor Positioning Module and Web Application Development

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Abstract: Due to the signal attenuation caused by construction materials, the satellite based mostly Global Positioning System (GPS) loses important power inside, poignant the desired coverage for receivers by a minimum of four satellites. Within an indoor positioning system (IPS) is employed to find objects or folks inside a building mistreatment sensory info. IPS has become inevitable in places like searching malls, hospitals, airports and alternative indoor venues wherever navigation and alternative location- based mostly services (LBS) will sway be indispensable. Ultra-wideband (UWB) may be a short-range radio technology which may be used for indoor positioning. UWB may be a radio technology which will use a awfully low energy for short-range, high-bandwidth communications over an outsized portion of the spectrum. This technique measures the period of time of sunshine between an object and several other receivers (anchors or locater Nodes). The thing to be caterpillar-tracked is supplied with a little tag (Locator Tag) that runs on battery power. It sends information (ID, ToF, timestamp) to the anchors or locater Nodes. Combining the info of locater Nodes, ends up in a positioning accuracy. By mistreatment this information internet application may be developed so we will simply find persons, machines, shops etc., in inside mistreatment UWB IPS technology.

Index Terms: Indoor Positioning System (IPS), Ultra- Wideband (UWB), Two-Way-Ranging (TWR), Real Time Location System (RTLS).

1. INTRODUCTION

Internal settings facilitate positioning and navigation in little coverage areas, Lower dynamics because of slower walking and speeds, Low weather influences like surfaces and walls. IPS progressively have become a spotlight of analysis is that the dominating technologies for positioning. GNSS do unwell within buildings. There may be different technologies that are used for indoor positioning, 5 of them are Proximity-based Systems, Wi-Fi Based Systems, Ultra Wide-band Systems, Acoustic Systems, and Infrared Systems. For the research, UWB IPS is taken as it has high bandwidth of approximately 500 Mhz [1] [2].

UWB could be a short-range radio technology which might be used for indoor positioning. UWB could be a radio technology that may use a really low energy for short-range, high-bandwidth communications over an outsized portion of the radio-frequency spectrum. UWB methodology measures the running time of light between an anchor and tag .Receiver work on battery power. The nodes have a set position within the

infrastructure and might use the time of light to calculate the space of the quality. Combining the information of locator Nodes, ends up in a positioning accuracy. By exploitation this information mobile application may be developed so user will simply find persons, machines, shops etc., in inside by UWB IPS technology. Here Decawave MDEK1001 module is employed.

There are number of requirements used for UWB positioning system, some of them are DWM1001 Two-Way-Ranging DRTLS Network, A UWB network consisting of locator nodes and receivers based on the DWM1001 module [2].

2. METHODOLOGY

Decawave MDEK1001 may be a module product that comes complete with code to permit system developers to quickly implement associate RTLS to suit their specific finish application, or add RTLS capability to associate existing system. The module could also be designed to behave as associate “anchor” one in every of the fastened nodes within the system or a “tag” one in every of the mobile set nodes within the system [3]. The module configuration could also be achieved either via Bluetooth victimization the companion application via associate SPI or UART association from associate external host or remotely from an internet consumer via the UWB.

Figure 1. Block Diagram of UWB IPS

The module additionally incorporates the Nordic Semiconductor nRF52832 IC providing the Bluetooth property used for configuration and therefore the microchip that runs the microcode that drives the DWM1001 and provides the RTLS sanctioning practicality [4]. Twelve DWM1001 modules are included in MDEK1001 Kit. A UWB DRTLS system uses a minimum of 3 anchors and a tag. To start the system a minimum of one among the locator node should be designed as an “initiator”. The leader anchor can begin and management the network and permit different anchors to hitch and type a network. The communication between anchors and tags is UWB communication and the communication between system and user is Bluetooth association [5] [6]. The anchors are placed in anti-clock wise direction [7] [8]. Tags location is determined in DRTLS manager. After formation of network a network id is created in DRTLS manager which is shown in figure 2.

Figure 2. Network ID in DRTLS Manager

The experiment was evaluated in a game room of dimensions 8x8 meters and 10x10 meters by placing anchors and tags. The accuracy is determined by placing the tag in distinct grid locations which is shown in figure 3. The actual and real value of (X, Y) coordinates are noted. The error is calculated by subtracting the actual and real value of (X, Y) coordinates. The average error is calculated by taking the mean of error coordinates. The average error obtained for a room of dimensions 8x8 meters is 0.5 meters. Parameters can be changed manually in DRTLS manger. By changing parameters manually, the average error obtained is 0.2 meters.

Figure 3. Anchors and Tag in Various Grid Positions

Gateway is developed with Decawave DWM 1001 modules by attaching module with Raspberry which are used to develop a web application so the user can monitor the system at any location [9] [10]. For Gateway arrangement, Raspberry Pi three model B (R3B) with an current flow and in the end coaxial cable, sixteen GB micro-SD card and a State card reader, 2x13 GPIO Header (long pin) for R3B, A laptop running Windows are the hardware parts employed in entrance readying [11] [12]. Raspberry Pi employed with DWM 1001 module for gateway which is shown in figure 4.

Figure 4. Gateway Setup

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

After creating a network, a gateway has to be created by attaching bridge node with Raspberry Pi 3 model B board and the position accuracy of anchors and tags has to be checked in VNC viewer. Then network monitoring is done by; using DRTLs Web-Manager. But by using this DRTLs Web-Manager the network can be monitored in certain range only. Web application is developed so that the network can be monitored at different ranges and in different locations. ‘

To develop a web application the anchors and tag data is sent to IBM Cloud by cloud computing. In IBM Cloud Node-Red Platform is used for developing the webpage by nodes connections. After developing the webpage, URL of the Node-Red page is copied. Paste the URL in a new tab then webpage is displayed.

The experiment is evaluated in the warehouse by placing the anchors and tags in the warehouse which is shown in figure 5. Anchors are placed in Anti-Clock wise direction and tags are movable devices. The positions of tags are calculated with respect to anchors positions and the tags position co-ordinates are displayed in Node-Red platform which is shown in figure 6.

Figure 5. Setup in Warehouse

Figure 6. Anchors and Tags Position Co-Ordinates in Node-Red

After knowing the tags position, the URL of Node-Red page is copied and pasted in a new tab then the webpage of Indoor Tracking is displayed which is shown in figure 7. The locations of anchors and tags are seen in the page. The location of tags changes by changing the tags position.

Tags

Figure 7. Locations of Anchors and Tags

Anchors

4. CONCLUSIONS

This paper discusses about the UWB technology in inside locations. UWB IPS is developed by using Decawave MDEK 1001 Kit which consists of DWM 1001 Modules. Each module can be configured as Anchors and tags. Working of Decawave DWM 1001 modules are evaluated in a game room of dimensions 8x8 and 10x10 meters and error is calculated. Gateway is developed by attaching bridge node with R3B and working is checked in vnc viewer. After gateway deployment, web application is developed by sending anchors and tags data to IBM cloud by cloud computing. Web application is developed in Node-Red platform in IBM cloud. URL of Node-Red is copied after developing the webpage and URL is pasted in new tab then webpage is displayed. The experiment is conducted in a warehouse by placing anchors in anti-clock wise direction and tag is a movable. Position co-ordinates of anchors and tags are checked in Node-Red and URL of Node-Red is pasted in new tab. Locations of anchors and tags are displayed in webpage.

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